

MINING the
EUROPEAN
ANTHROPOSPHERE

Anthropogenic Resource Classification

Why?

The management of resources requires consistent, reliable and transparent estimates about the future of the world's mineral commodity supply.

Geological Resource Classifications (GRCs) assess the availability of energy and mineral resources, which depends in turn on science and technology as well as environmental, social and economic factors. GRCs are key elements in the project cycle of virtually all large mining operations and thus stand at the beginning of many value chains of modern society. **Anthropogenic Resource Classifications (ARCs)** complement GRCs by estimating the **availability of raw materials from secondary sources** such as mining residues, buildings, infrastructure, consumer goods, landfills, incineration residues and all sources from the material life cycle stages, including production, use and end-of-life.

ARCs helps **government authorities, policy makers, investors and decision makers in the waste management sector** to carry out strategic resource planning and make sound judgements on the potential of material sourcing projects.

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Who we are

We are the pan-European Expert Network on **Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA)** with stakeholders from more than 32 countries. Our **aim** is to initiate the classification of Anthropogenic Resources.

What we do

We strengthen the European Research Area by:

- Developing standards and guidelines for characterizing, evaluating and classifying and reporting Anthropogenic Resources. This includes the collection, comparison and harmonization of practices.
- Providing an interdisciplinary platform for academics, professionals, industrial and government representatives to share research findings and professional knowledge on material recovery and secondary raw material production and supply.
- Supporting the Expert Group on Resource Classification (EGRC) at the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) in developing and promoting the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) with respect to Anthropogenic Resources.

Contact Us

Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) Action
Mining the European Anthroposphere

Email: info@minea-network.eu

Web: www.minea-network.eu

Authors: Dr. Ulrich Kral, Technische Universität Wien, Austria
Prof. Dr. Soraya Heuss-Aßbichler, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Germany
Mr. Mark Simoni, Norwegian Geological Survey, Norway

Proofreading: Andrew Clarke

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